

Concept 5 – Oysters as food

Part of the AquaVitae MOOC reading material

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A brief history of oyster production over time

Archeological findings indicate that oysters were an integrated part of the diets in coastal communities already during the stone- and bronze age, and later also in the Viking culture. Today, molluscs are the third largest category of farmed seafood by both quantity and value, accounting for 21% (17.2 millions tons) of all global aquaculture production by weight in 2019, worth approximately 274.76 billion dollars, of which approximately 6.1 million tons are oysters, worth approximately 7.39 billion USD (FAO 2022). The oyster production has, however, struggled with overexploitation of wild populations and periodic failures in culture linked to pathogen outbreaks both in historical (Bustel et al. 2009, Wijsman et al. 2019) and in recent times (Pernet et al. 2016, Wijsman et al. 2019). A common tool to address these challenges has been the introduction of new oyster species which has led to dispersal of invasive species (both as target species in aquaculture and as accidental transmission with culture species) and exacerbated disease challenges (Botta et al., 2020).

In Europe, the European flat oyster, *Ostrea edulis*, was the principal oyster from Roman times to the 19th century, yet from the 18th century onward, increasing pressure on the oyster populations led to depletion of native oyster beds (Heral, 1989). From 1860, due to a shortage of flat oysters, the Portuguese cupped oysters, *Crassostrea angulata*, was imported from Portugal to France, and from there, the species spread quickly. A massive mortality of flat oysters from 1920 to 1922 firmly established the production supremacy of *C. angulata*, however between 1970 and 1973, mass mortalities struck again, causing the total disappearance of the Portuguese oyster (Heral, 1989). This was in turn compensated for by a massive import of the Pacific oyster, *Magallana (Crassostrea) gigas* (Bustel 2009), and the production of the Pacific oyster soon exceeded the previous production of *C. angulata*. In South Africa the Pacific Oyster was imported for aquaculture in 1973, and in Namibia oysters have been cultured since the 1980s. The Namibian oyster industry is, however, supported by imported seed due to lack of hatcheries. Oyster aquaculture in Brazil started in the 1960s-1970s in an artisanal way. The Pacific oyster was introduced between the 70s and 80s and now constitutes the bulk of the production (Ramos et al., 1986; Suplicy et al., 2022). Hatchery production of the species was started in 1991 and supported the expansion of the industry during the 1990s-2000s.

Importance of oysters in the global aquaculture production

Currently, oyster aquaculture is heavily dominated by Asia (primarily by China), which comprised 87% of global oyster aquaculture production by weight and 88% of global aquaculture production by value (FAO 2022). After Asia, the two largest oyster producing

nations are The United States and France. In contrast to Asia where oyster production is expanding, in France there is a general 0.05% per annum decline in oyster production since 1950 (Pernet et al., 2016). The main species in production is the Pacific oyster. The species originates from Japan but has been introduced to all continents except Antarctica for aquaculture purposes (Padilla 2010), and is now, in addition to being one of the most important aquaculture species, also one of the most widely introduced marine invertebrates (Ruesink et al. 2005, Sousa et al. 2009). In a global context, the Pacific oyster represents 97% of the total oyster production worldwide, and 39% of the oyster production around the Atlantic (FAO 2022). In addition to the Pacific oyster, the main oyster species of economic importance in the Atlantic region are the native European flat oyster (*O. edulis*, in Europe), the mangrove oyster (*Crassostrea gasar*, in Brazil), and the Eastern oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*, in the US). In Brazil, the native oyster *Crassostrea rhizophorae* is also cultured, although in small volumes, and in South Africa, the native oyster *Striostrea margaritacea* is harvested from wild populations also in small quantities (Haupt et al., 2010).

Markets and products

There is a wide diversity of markets and products of oysters. Oysters are almost exclusively sold as fresh raw products, and in the case of France all the production is sold fresh (Erwan et al., 1998). Here, oysters have historically been considered a luxury, festive product (Buestel et al., 2009), which is true in particular for the European flat oyster which is considered to be a premium product, known mainly by connoisseurs and available in small quantities at high prices (Girard and Mariojouis 2001). In the US, an increasing proportion of the production is channeled into fresh and frozen half-shell form for the foodservice trade. Additionally, eastern oysters are also used as fresh and frozen breaded oysters, either raw or pre-cooked. In Brazil, products are more diverse, and oysters are marketed as whole, freshly shucked, steam-cooked, boiled or frozen (Barroso, 2004). In South Africa, processed products, e.g. smoked and canned oysters and the majority of frozen oyster products are imported (Olivier 2011). In terms of consumer perception, while infrequent oyster consumers preferred the concept of wild-caught oysters, more frequent oyster (and thus perhaps more knowledgeable) consumers preferred the farmed variety (Kecinski et. al, 2017).

In terms of target markets, the strategies differ between geographical regions. In Scandinavia where oyster production is underdeveloped, the production does not cover the market demand. All production is consumed locally, and imports are increasing. This also infers premium prices on locally produced oysters. Similarly in Brazil, most of the production is for the local market, although farmers have the ambition to expand to the export market (de Sampaio et al., 2017). In South Africa wild populations of the native oyster *S. margaritacea* are currently harvested (Haupt, et al., 2010) and used locally (Branch et al., 2002) as neither wild harvested, nor farmed, oysters are competitive in the export markets (Britz, 2007) due to South Africa's lack of international standards of health certification which prevent export to most countries. In other situations (e.g. Ireland and Namibia), the focus is on the export market (Renwick, 2018, Chiripanhura et al., 2016). In Namibia e.g. only a small proportion of the production is sold on the local market (Chiripanhura et al., 2016). In France, which can be characterized as a mature market, there is a balance between domestic consumption and exports, and intriguingly, also of imports. In the US, fresh oysters are mainly produced locally, while processed oysters (canned) are imported from China and South Korea (both farmed and wild oysters, Lipton et al., 1994).

Nutritional values of oysters

Shellfish, such as oysters, are regarded as excellent dietary sources of various health related nutrients not available in terrestrial based protein (Venugopal and Gopakumar, 2017; Wright, et al. 2018), and are considered to be among the most nutrient dense seafood available (Hällström et al., 2019). The protein content varies between 5-14 g/100g raw flesh depending on season and postharvest handling (FAO/INFOOD; Zhu et al., 2018) and is of high quality as it contains all essential amino acids. Moreover, oysters are low in total fat and in saturated fats, and rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs, approximately 45% of total fatty acids) with high levels of DHA (approximately 20% of total fatty acids) and EPA (approximately 18% of total fatty acids, Zhu et al., 2018). Oysters also contain high levels of vitamins, in particular vitamin B12, as well as trace elements and minerals as selenium, calcium, iron, magnesium, copper and zinc (Zhu et al., 2018), while being low in sodium. Nutritional values may vary with season and are at its highest just before spawning (Orban et al., 2004).

Food safety aspects

These positive health benefits of oysters, however, need to be balanced by potential health risks. As filter-feeders, bivalves accumulate substances from the water. Certain phytoplankton produce biotoxins (HABs, Harmful Algae Blooms, FAO, 2004) that are accumulated in the oysters and can cause Paralytic Shellfish Poisoning (Bricelj and Shumway, 1998) and Diarrhetic Shellfish Poisoning (Karlsson 2007), among other, in humans as the oysters are consumed. Moreover, as the use of coastal zones is intensified, transmission of anthropogenic contaminants into the sea increases. Oysters may accumulate heavy metals and tend to reflect local contaminant concentrations (Boening, 1999; Bourgoin, 1990; Cunningham, 1979; Phillips, 1993; Rodney et al., 2007; Jennings et al., 2016), making them ideally suited for contaminant monitoring (in Mid-Atlantic coastal waters, EPA, 2000). This however, also highlights the need for good water quality to avoid detrimental effects on consumer health. Targeted heavy metals and trace elements include arsenic, cadmium, copper, lead, nickel and mercury. Another type of contaminant is faecal contamination. Wastewater treatment plants or runoff from land are particularly important pathways for the transmission of human pathogens from faecal matter into coastal areas, where the pathogens are taken up by oysters. As oysters are in general eaten raw, viruses and bacteria may consequently pose a threat to human health (EFSA, 2015), with norovirus being the most commonly occurring pathogen in the northern hemisphere (Public Health Agency of Canada, 2015; Beckman and Toljander. 2017). Pathogenic *Vibrio* species are also an increasing threat (De Witte et al., 2014, CFIA, 2015).

To address these issues, regulations to ensure food safety in the European Union were put in place in 2004 (EC, 2004) and classifications of water quality based on the concentration of the faecal indicator organism *Escherichia coli* was established (Fox et al., 2019). According to the regulations, specific production areas have been designated and classified according to potential health risks, and monitoring programs have been established in most industrial regions to detect the presence of specific biotoxin-producing phytoplankton and biotoxins in oysters. If biotoxins are discovered in sampled oysters, harvest is prohibited for some time, causing detrimental effects on production (Larsson, 2005; Persson, 2014; SCB, 2017). A temporary loss of production may, however, be preferred over a significant loss in consumer trust, that may have long term impacts on market demand. In Brazil, a Hygienic-sanitary program, with monitoring of *E. coli* and phytotoxins has been established by the government, but the program is, until now, only implemented in the state Santa Catarina. Florianópolis (in Santa Catarina state) is often referred to as the national capital of oysters in Brazil, which attracts tourists and supports the local economy. Similar structures also exist in the US (the

National Shellfish Sanitation Program NSSP). The NSSP Guide for the Control of Molluscan Shellfish is the Federal/State cooperative program, recognized by the US Food and Drug Administration for the purpose of sanitary control of shellfish produced or sold for human consumption. In Namibia, the oyster production is planned to be governed by the Namibian Model Shellfish Sanitation Monitoring Program (NMSSMP). The regulations are drafted but not yet legally enforceable.

The adoption of guidelines and the establishment of food safety systems are vital for ensuring healthy food and to mitigate risks associated with oyster consumption (Venugopal and Gopakumar, 2017; Wright et al., 2018), and absence of such structures can act as trade barriers as experienced in Africa. Moreover, for bacterial and virus contamination, heat treatment (i.e. cooking) and high pressure treatment (HPT) may reduce the risk of human pathogen contamination. In some situations, e.g. in the case of biotoxins that are heat resistant, and for human pathogens, contamination can also be handled before processing, e.g. by live-storage in systems supplied with clean water (depuration, McLeod et al., 2017).

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